

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF CONJUNCTIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Rustamova Sevinch, Fayzullayeva Sabrina, Islomova Feruza, Kabilova Feruza

Languages Students of NSU

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Annotation. *This article reports the differences and similarities of conjunctions in English and Uzbek languages. Conjunctions serve as a resource for learners and educators, enabling them to express relationships between actions and thoughts, and helps to understand the usage of it across these two different languages.*

Key words: *conjunctions, similarities, differences, comparison, grammatical features.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье сообщается о различиях и сходствах союзов в английском и узбекском языках. Союзы служат ресурсом для учащихся и преподавателей, позволяя им выразить отношения между действиями и мыслями, а также помогают понять их использование в этих двух разных языках.*

Ключевые слова: *союзы, сходство, различия, сравнение, грамматические особенности.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi bog'lovchilarning farqlari va o'xshash tomonlari haqida ma'lumot beradi. Bog'lovchilar o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun manba bo'lib, ularga harakatlar va fikrlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni ifodalash imkonini beradi va bu ikki xil tilda ulardan foydalanishni tushunishga yordam beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *bog'lovchilar, o'xshashliklar, farqlar, qiyoslash, grammatik belgilar.*

Conjunctions play an essential part to link words, clauses, and phrases together. They allow us to create more complex and subtle expressions. Although English and Uzbek languages have similar functions through conjunctions, but they also serve different characteristics determined by their linguistic structures and contexts.

Both English and Uzbek use 3 types of conjunctions: coordinating, subordinating, and correlative conjunctions.

Coordinating conjunctions (biriktiruv bog'lovchilar) allow you to join words, phrases, and clauses of equal grammatical rank in a sentence. The most common coordinating conjunctions are "for" (chunki), "and" (va), "nor" (na), "but" (ammo), "or" (yoki), "yet" (biroq), and "so" (shuning uchun); you can remember them by using the mnemonic device FANBOYS.¹

Harry didn't recognize the third owl, a handsome tawny one, but he knew at once where it had come from, because in addition to a third package, it was carrying a letter bearing the Hogwarts crest.²

- "Men uning xon qizini olish maqsadi borlig'ini bilmayman", - dedi kulimsirab, - "biroq ul xon qizini olsa arzimaydirgan yigit emas..."³

Subordinating conjunctions (tobun bog'lovchilar) join independent and dependent clauses. A subordinating conjunction can signal a cause-and-effect relationship, a contrast, or some other kind of relationship between the clauses. Common subordinating conjunctions are

"because" (chunki), "since" (toki), "as" (kabi, qachonki), "although" (garchi), "though" (bo'lsa-da), "while" (holbuki), and "whereas" (biroq).⁴

Hokimlarga garchi to'g'ri bo'lg'anda ham, dag'alroq so'z aytish o'limni tilash bilan teng edi.⁵

This separation from his spellbooks had been a real problem for Harry, because his teachers at Hogwarts had given him a lot of holiday work.⁶

Correlative conjunctions (juft bog'lovchilar) are pairs of conjunctions that work together. Some examples are "either/or" (Yoki...yoki), "neither/nor" (Na...na), and "not only/but also" (Na faqat...balki...ham).⁷

1 <https://www.grammarly.com/blog/parts-of-speech/conjunctions/>

2 Rowling J. K. Harry Potter and the Prisoner of the Azkaban: Bloomsbury, 1999. p 11

3 Abdulla Q. O'tkan kunlar. T.: "Navro'z", 2019. 20 b

4 <https://www.grammarly.com/blog/parts-of-speech/conjunctions/>

5 Abdulla Q. O'tkan kunlar. T.: "Navro'z", 2019. 74 b

6 Rowling J. K. Harry Potter and the Prisoner of the Azkaban: Bloomsbury, 1999. p 8

7 <https://www.grammarly.com/blog/parts-of-speech/conjunctions/>

Neither Ron nor Hermione felt like going, however, so they and Harry wandered onto the grounds...⁸

Yo bir-birlari bilan kim ko'p ishlashga musobaqa o'ynashgan, yoki o'zlari shunaqangi chaqqon ishlashga o'rganib qolishgan bo'lsa kerak deb o'ylardim.⁹

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that the grammatical systems of English and Uzbek are different according to their linguistic classification. Despite some differences, the examples given in this article show some similarities in the formation and the use of conjunctions in both English and Uzbek languages.

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